

Applying an ontology-aware zero-shot LLM prompting approach for information extraction in Greek: the case of DIAVGIEA gov gr

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Abstract

Large Language Models (LLMs) have attracted considerable attention, primarily due to their potential to revolutionize sectors that heavily rely on textual information. Governance is one such sector. Public administrations around the globe produce millions of documents including laws, administrative decisions and acts (e.g., travel/budget approvals) that contain valuable information in unstructured way. The documents are usually stored at document-centered repositories. As a result the actual data of the documents cannot be further searched or processed. The availability of structured metadata of the documents (e.g., who has traveled, where, when) could further enhance the searching and processing of the documents as well as enable data analytics. The construction of metadata can be done through information extraction approaches such as Named Entity Recognition (NER), Relation Extraction (RE) and Event Extraction (EE) on the documents. LLMs are recently used successfully for information extraction tasks, while ontologies are traditionally used for meaningful data modeling. The aim of the paper is to apply and evaluate an ontology-aware zero-shot LLM prompting approach for information extraction in Greek language documents available in DIAVGIEA.gov.gr - the Greek Open Government portal for administrative documents. The evaluation assesses various LLM models/sizes for various difficulties of information extraction tasks. Overall the results are very promising, since most LLM models, even smaller ones, performed very well for all tasks in Greek.

CCS Concepts

• **Computing methodologies** → **Information extraction**; • **Applied computing** → **E-government**; • **Information systems** → **Ontologies**; **Document structure**.

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Keywords

Information extraction, NER, LLM, Ontology, Greek, Public administration

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1 Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs) have attracted considerable attention, primarily due to their potential to revolutionize sectors that heavily rely on textual information. Governance is one such sector. Public administrations around the globe produce and handle a vast amount of data usually in the form of documents including laws, administrative decisions and acts related to e.g., expenditure approvals, project assignments, personnel hiring/relocation and payments. All these documents contain valuable information that cannot be further processed since it is provided only as unstructured text. The structuring of existing public administration documents, by providing rich metadata accompanying the document, would enhance the searching of the documents as well as enable advanced data analytics that were not previously possible. For example, an administrative act (i.e., document) for a "Travel approval" can be accompanied with metadata such as the "traveler", "origin", "destination", "transport mode" and "expense". Such metadata would enable for example the identification of "Travel approval" documents from origin X for further processing or the summarizing of travel expenses for specific "travelers".

The extraction of the metadata from the documents can be done using information extraction approaches such as Named Entity Recognition (NER), Relation Extraction (RE) and Event Extraction (EE) on the documents. Information extraction was traditionally done using rule-based methods, statistical methods and recently also machine learning methods (demanding for substantial labeled data). The last years, deep learning and more specifically Generative AI - LLMs are successfully employed for information extraction tasks [14, 27]. They perform very well even with no previous fine-tuning using N-shot [1] or even zero-shot learning [8].

Information extraction is beneficial to be driven by an ontology (or data model) that defines the concepts and their relations that underlie the domain at hand [16]. For example, an ontology to model “Travel approvals” could contain concepts such as the “trip”, “traveler”, “origin” as well as relations such as “a trip has a traveler” or “a trip has an origin”. Thus the entities identified through information extraction would formulate instances of the ontology that all of them together can form a Knowledge Graph. Ontologies and Knowledge graphs enable the meaningful data modeling and also reasoning. Recently a number of approaches have been proposed that combine LLMs and ontologies in order to perform information extraction (e.g., [8, 9, 16, 20]).

In the context of Greek public administration, documents (pdf) including administrative acts and decisions are published at DIAVGEIA¹. DIAVGEIA (meaning clarity in Greek) is the Greek Open Government national portal where most of the public sector administrative acts and decisions are published forming a huge collection currently containing more than 60 million documents. While, the collection is continuously increasing with around 20 thousand new entries per day. The information published at DIAVGEIA includes limited metadata (e.g., the signer/publisher of the act/decision) and unstructured documents (pdfs).

In the frame of the paper we apply and evaluate an ontology-aware zero-shot LLM prompting approach for information extraction on Greek documents from DIAVGEIA. We evaluate various LLM models with various sizes that understand Greek (GPT, Mistral, Llama) based on information extraction tasks of increased complexity. The key outcome of the paper is that existing pre-trained LLMs (even smaller ones) are capable of performing information extraction tasks in Greek without further fine-tuning since they successfully identified the majority of the information (entities and their relations) in the documents.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents background and related work, section 3 describes the methodology employed, section 4 presents the main results and section 5 contains the conclusions and future work.

2 Background and related work

2.1 Overview of DIAVGEIA platform

DIAVGEIA publishes a number of 35 different categories of act types including expenditure approvals, payment finalizations, project assignments, building permits, budget approvals, publishing of balance accounts and donations. Some of the existing categories are very vague, such as “Other individual administrative acts” that contains almost 10M documents including personnel hiring, appointment, relocation etc. “Travel approvals” including around 1M documents are also categorized at the “Other individual administrative acts”. The majority of the published documents could be considered as transaction/event containers including information about transactions/events occurring in the frame of public administration [31]. For example, the act types payment finalizations and project assignments could be considered as transactions/events.

¹<https://diavgeia.gov.gr/>

2.2 Ontologies and Knowledge Graphs for structuring data

Ontologies and Knowledge graphs (KG) are widely used as a paradigm to structure large collections of data in a meaningful way. Ontologies provide the structure (concepts, properties) and constraints to model the data at a KG. However, traditional KGs do not have a time dimension by design, therefore they cannot efficiently represent dynamic information (e.g., transactions) [30].

In this context the literature has proposed the use of Event Centric Knowledge Graphs (ECKGs) as an efficient way to represent dynamic information including temporal facts about entities, events and their relations [25]. The event is usually considered as something that happens at a particular place and time [23], therefore the concepts “time” and “place” are very common in the ECKG ontologies. Except from the “time” and “place”, the concept “agent” is very common as a participant (with various roles e.g., event starter, event receiver) to an event. In the domain of public administration, various ECKG models have also been proposed [6, 29, 30]. The last models adopt an approach of representing the events as hierarchical trees having the agent as a root. This approach is more efficient in identifying all the events of an agent [2, 5] thus enabling Public Administration to have a more comprehensive 360 view of core agent types such as citizens, businesses or public servants.

2.3 LLMs for information extraction

Recently, LLMs were successfully used for information extraction tasks [27] such as Named Entity Recognition (NER) [14], Relation Extraction (RE) [26] and Event Extraction (EE) [10, 15, 28]. Various low-resource methods are used to apply LLMs for information extraction including zero-shot learning [4, 7], few-shot learning [1], in-Context Learning [12] etc. Some approaches use ontology-aware prompts for information extraction in order to improve performance and get better structured results [8, 9, 16, 20]. Specifically, [8] adopts a structured way of iterative prompting based on an ontology in order to structure textual information based on a provided ontology. In the frame of public administration LLMs are used for information extraction mainly from legal documents [3, 17, 22]. A similar application of LLMs in Public Administrations includes QA directly on structured (non-document) Open Government Data Portals without previous information extraction [18]. However the later approach is only applicable to structured data portals.

The paper at hand, builds upon existing approaches on ontology-aware prompting and further extends them to fit at the domain of public administration (i.e., DIAVGEIA). The proposed approach is then evaluated at Greek language documents.

3 Methodology for Information Extraction

The aim of the paper is to apply and evaluate an ontology-aware zero-shot LLM prompting approach for information extraction on Greek documents from DIAVGEIA. The methodology steps followed towards this direction are:

- Select a specific type of document available in DIAVGEIA. We selected “Travel approvals” since they are very popular (1M documents), and also comprise various interesting cases for information extraction tasks (described in section 4)

- Create a modular (i.e., extendable) ontology/model (figure 1) to represent the information produced through information extraction. The generated ontology is based on ECKG models (section 2.2), models/ontologies about travels and transportation (e.g., [11, 13, 19, 21, 24]), official public administration documents (e.g., travel authorization forms²) describing travel orders/approvals and on the study of various "Travel approvals" available in DIAVGEIA. The produced model does not aim to be exhaustive but acts as a basis for experimentation in the frame of the paper.
- Create a prompt template (figure 2) to be used for information extraction tasks on "Travel approvals". The prompt is based on the produced ontology and is also inspired by similar ontology-aware prompting approaches such as [8] but further extends them. The prompt can easily be extended to include more concepts of the ontology.
- Apply the prompt on various "Travel approval" documents using various LLM models and evaluate the performance.

The model (figure 1) adopts the modular structure proposed by [30] to represent transactions/events in the frame of public administration. This structure includes some main concepts such as the Agent (Citizen, Business, Public Servant), Event (in our case "Travel approval") and Date but can be further extended with domain concepts related to an event in a modular way without affecting the main structure. In our case, in order to represent the details related to a travel approval, more concepts are added such as the "Trip" (some ontologies use the term "Travel") that is defined as an "activity wherein a Person(s) is transported from one location to another via some mode" usually for a specific reason [13]. Based on this definition the trip is associated to a "Traveler" (i.e., Public Servant), a "Start/End date" (these are different from the date of travel approval), "Origin/Destination" location, "Reason" e.g., travel for a meeting or a conference (some ontologies use the term "Purpose"), "Transport mode" e.g., air, rail, car, bus (some ontologies use the term "Means of travel") and also the expected "Expense". There is also a self relation "includes" of the trip representing complex trips with multiple trip legs. The model can easily be extended to represent other transactions/event by adding more domain specific concepts that are linked to the main structure (Agent, Event, Date).

The prompt template (figure 2) consists of four main parts. The first part contains the overall instructions to the LLM (i.e., to separate the provided text based on the specified format considering the field descriptions.). The second part (<Format>) describes the format of the expected result. The format represents partially the ontology (figure 1) in the form of triples (e.g., Trip_{N} has_traveler <Traveler>.). The part of the ontology that is represented in the prompt includes the "Trip", the "Public Servant" (traveler), the origin/destination "Location" and the start/end "Date". The format can easily be extended to include the whole ontology. Note also that the format assumes that multiple (i.e., {N}) trips may be represented in the provided text. The third part (<Descriptions>) includes descriptions of the relations used in the ontology that are part of the format. The description provides contextual information about the relation including also its cardinality (e.g., one and only one). The fourth part (<Greek Text>) contains the Greek text extracted from

the "Travel approval" document. Similar prompt templates can be produced for other act types of DIAVGEIA. We experimented both with an English and a Greek version of the prompt using the same structure. In order to improve the paper readability the English prompt and the produced results are included in the paper.

4 Experimental results and analysis

This section presents the experimental evaluation results based on the application of the proposed approach on the DIAVGEIA documents. It also includes a description of the dataset used for the experimentation.

4.1 Dataset characteristics

Based on our study, we identified three main categories of travel approvals available in DIAVGEIA:

- Documents describing one trip of one person (1p1t).
- Documents describing multiple trips of one person (1pNt). This, for example may contain the same trip (origin, destination) repeated in different dates or even completely different trips (figure 3 Example 1).
- Documents describing multiple trips of multiple persons (NpNt). This, for example may include the same trip (origin, destination, start/end date) for multiple persons, or trips that differ in terms of origin/destination for multiple persons (figure 3 Example 2). Usually the trips included in the same document have the same reason (e.g., move to a conference or for participating at a meeting)

Some interesting remarks about the travel approval documents include: i) in some cases the trip is described as "same day" without explicitly mentioning the end date, ii) the information about the trip within the document may be provided either as completely unstructured text or as structured text (e.g. bullet points) or in a table, iii) in case the document includes multiple trips (cases 1pNt or NpNt) the trips are either described independently or in some cases the descriptions are merged within the text, iv) in some cases the information about multiple trips may be grouped per e.g., start/end date (see figure 3 Example 1), v) in some cases the origin of the trip is not explicitly mentioned and should be inferred based on the name of the public administration approving the travel (e.g., Municipality of Thessaloniki -> Thessaloniki), vi) in some cases the name of the traveler is not defined explicitly at the piece of text describing the trip, but is mentioned only his/her position (e.g., minister) while in other part of the text the name and the position are linked.

4.2 Evaluation setup and results

In order to evaluate the ontology-aware zero-shot LLM prompting approach presented in section 3 we used 10 documents for each of the three categories (1p1t, 1pNt, NpNt) of travel approvals (30 documents in total). We extracted the text (the main text of the document describing the travel approval, ignoring any headers or preliminary text) from the documents and formulated similar prompts based on the template (figure 2). In case the document includes tables, the extracted text does not follow a table format. Then we applied in chat mode the same prompt at various free or open source LLMs that understand Greek and we had access. The

²<https://www.gsa.gov/system/files/GSA87-20.pdf>

Figure 1: Ontology/model to represent travel approvals.

Separate the following piece of <Greek Text> exclusively into fields with the following <Format> taking into account the <Descriptions> of the fields. Return the result exclusively using the provided <Format>.

```
<Format>:
Trip_{N} has_traveler <Traveler>.
Trip_{N} has_origin <Origin>.
Trip_{N} has_destination <Destination>.
Trip_{N} has_start_date <Start_Date>.
Trip_{N} has_end_date <End_Date>.
```

Where {N} is the number of the trip.

```
<Descriptions>:
Traveler: <The name of one and only one person who is traveling>.
Origin: <The one and only one place - city from where the trip starts>.
Destination: <The one and only one place - city that is the destination of the trip>.
Start_Date: <The one and only one date that the trip starts>.
End_Date: <The one and only one date that the trip ends>.
```

```
<Greek Text>:
--- THE GREEK TEXT OF THE ACT FOLLOWS---
```

Figure 2: The English ontology-aware prompt used for information extraction (uses a part of the proposed ontology - figure 1).

LLMs used are the GPT4o mini, Mistral 7B, Mistral 2 Large (123B), Llama 3.1 8B, Llama 3.1 70B and Llama 3.1 405B. GPT4o mini was accessed through free chatGPT while Mistral and Llama models were accessed through the Amazon Bedrock playground that the authors had access. The returned results are manually checked and compared to the ground truth. For example figure 4 contains the results returned by GPT 4o mini for the Example 1 and Example 2 acts of figure 3. Other LLMs produce similar results.

The aim of the evaluation is to access models of various sizes at information extraction tasks of different complexity (i.e., 1p1t, 1pNt, NpNt). The metrics used for the evaluation are precision, recall and F1. The granularity for measuring the true positives (triples correctly identified), false positives (triples wrongly identified) and false negatives (triples missing from the returned result) is the triple (as defined in the expected format at the prompt).

The evaluation results are presented at figures 5 and 6. Generally speaking, all models performed very well except from Mistral 7B. Mistral 7B in many cases identified correctly the requested triples, however it also included in the result many structured or even unstructured information not requested. Regarding the case 1p1t, all models except Mistral 7B, achieved very high scores. For more complex tasks (1pNt and NpNt) the scores are somehow reduced but still very high. Although we expected that the scores for the NpNt cases will be worse than the 1pNt, this was not confirmed. A possible explanation is that 1pNt documents used for the evaluation had some peculiarities in the definition of dates (e.g., multiple "same day" trips or origin not explicitly mentioned). Another interesting point is that within the same task (1pNt, 1pNt, NpNt) the scores are slightly improved when the size of the model increases, however even small models perform very well. We also experimented with a same-structured prompt in Greek and the results were similar.

Example act 1:

Τη μετακίνηση της μόνιμης υπαλλήλου του κλάδου ΠΕ αρχαιολόγων κας X - M, Προϊσταμένης της ΕΦΑ

Traveler

Start dates

Ημερομηνία αναχώρησης: α) 10-10-24, β) 16-10-24, γ) 21-10-24, δ) 25-10-24, ε) 31-10-24

End dates

Ημερομηνία επανόδου: α) 10-10-24, β) 16-10-24, γ) 21-10-24, δ) 25-10-24, ε) 31-10-24

Origins and destination as: origin – destination - origin

Τόπος μετακίνησης: α) Αιανή – Πύργοι - Αιανή, β) Αιανή – Σπηλιά - Αιανή, γ) Αιανή – Πύργοι - Αιανή, δ) Αιανή – Σπηλιά - Αιανή, ε) Αιανή – Πύργοι - Αιανή

Example act 2:

Same day travel

ΑΥΓΗΜΕΡΟΝ ΜΕΤΑΚΙΝΗΣΕΙΣ ΠΕΡΙΦΕΡΕΙΑΚΩΝ ΣΥΜΒΟΥΛΩΝ ΣΤΙΣ 05-10-2015

Α/Α	ΗΜΕΡΟΜΗΝΙΑ	ΟΝΟΜΑΤΕΠΩΝΥΜΟ	ΠΡΟΟΡΙΣΜΟΣ	ΛΟΓΟΣ ΜΕΤΑΚΙΝΗΣΗΣ
1	05-10-2015	Γ. Κ.	ΦΛΩΡΙΝΑ ↔ ΚΟΖΑΝΗ ΟΔΙΚΩΣ (ΜΕ Ι.Χ.)	ΣΥΜΜΕΤΟΧΗ ΣΤΗΝ ΟΙΚΟΝΟΜΙΚΗ ΕΠΙΤΡΟΠΗ
2	05-10-2015	Β. Π.	ΜΑΝΙΑΚΟΙ ΚΑΣΤΟΡΙΑΣ ↔ ΚΟΖΑΝΗ ΟΔΙΚΩΣ (ΜΕ Ι.Χ.)	ΣΥΜΜΕΤΟΧΗ ΣΤΗΝ ΟΙΚΟΝΟΜΙΚΗ ΕΠΙΤΡΟΠΗ

Figure 3: DIAVGEIA acts. Example 1: multiple trips of one person (1pNt). Example 2: multiple trips of multiple persons (NpNt)

Example 1:

```
Trip_1 has_traveler X. M. .
Trip_1 has_origin Αιανή.
Trip_1 has_destination Πύργοι.
Trip_1 has_start_date 10-10-24.
Trip_1 has_end_date 10-10-24.

Trip_2 has_traveler X. M. .
Trip_2 has_origin Αιανή.
Trip_2 has_destination Σπηλιά.
Trip_2 has_start_date 16-10-24.
Trip_2 has_end_date 16-10-24.

Trip_3 has_traveler X. M. .
Trip_3 has_origin Αιανή.
Trip_3 has_destination Πύργοι.
Trip_3 has_start_date 21-10-24.
Trip_3 has_end_date 21-10-24.
```

```
Trip_4 has_traveler X. M. .
Trip_4 has_origin Αιανή.
Trip_4 has_destination Σπηλιά.
Trip_4 has_start_date 25-10-24.
Trip_4 has_end_date 25-10-24.

Trip_5 has_traveler X. M. .
Trip_5 has_origin Αιανή.
Trip_5 has_destination Πύργοι.
Trip_5 has_start_date 31-10-24.
Trip_5 has_end_date 31-10-24.
```

Example 2:

```
Trip_1 has_traveler Γ. Κ. .
Trip_1 has_origin Φλώρινα.
Trip_1 has_destination Κοζάνη.
Trip_1 has_start_date 05-10-2015.
Trip_1 has_end_date 05-10-2015.

Trip_2 has_traveler Β. Π. .
Trip_2 has_origin Μανιάκοι Καστοριάς.
Trip_2 has_destination Κοζάνη.
Trip_2 has_start_date 05-10-2015.
Trip_2 has_end_date 05-10-2015.
```

Figure 4: Result returned by GPT 4o mini for the Example 1 and Example 2 acts of figure 3.

Some qualitative results (mainly problems) per LLM model based on the experimentation are the following:

- GPT 4o mini: had some issues in identifying "same day" trips and in identifying a city (e.g. origin) based on a public administration name.
- Mistral 7B: we made some experiment using an equivalent Greek prompt, in this case only Mistral 7B first returned a translation of the prompt in English and then all the rest result. It also tends to transform all the provided text into

triples thus providing many triples not included in the requested format and in some cases including also many free text. It also had difficulties in identifying a city (e.g. origin) based on a public administration name (e.g., Municipality of Thessaloniki). In some cases it also had difficulties in separating the father name from the name -surname of the traveler. However, in one NpNt case it correctly identified the requested information while other models had problems.

LLM model	1 person 1 trip			1 person N trips			N persons N trips		
	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall	F1
GPT 4o mini	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,85	0,92	1,00	0,99	0,99
Mistral 7B	0,25	0,78	0,38	0,11	0,54	0,18	0,49	0,83	0,62
Mistral 2 Large (123B)	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,89	0,94	1,00	0,94	0,97
Llama 3.1 8B	1,00	0,94	0,97	1,00	0,89	0,94	0,94	0,93	0,93
Llama 3.1 70B	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,94	0,97	1,00	0,98	0,99
Llama 3.1 405B	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,99	0,99	1,00	0,98	0,99

Figure 5: Evaluation results per LLM model for each of the three categories 1p1t, 1pNt and NpNt.

Figure 6: F1 score for each of the three categories 1p1t, 1pNt and NpNt for various model sizes

- Mistral 2 Large: successfully identified the city based on a public administration name but had some issues in identifying "same day" trips.
- Llama 3.1 8B: had some difficulties identifying a city (e.g. origin) based on a public administration name (e.g., Municipality of Thessaloniki).
- Llama 3.1 70B: was more "polite" than Llama 8B by adding some text before/after the returned triples. It successfully identified the city based on a public administration name. In one case it identified the possibility to define different trips and asks to do so or not. It also identified "same day" trips but failed to correctly assign the end date.
- Llama 3.1 405B: successfully identified the city based on a public administration name and also used the correct noun or person names.

5 Conclusions and future work

This paper applied and evaluated an ontology-aware zero-shot LLM prompting approach for Greek documents available at DIAVGEIA. The results are very promising since even small in size LLM models performed very well.

The use of ontologies to guide LLMs in data modeling seems promising, but it may be challenging to expanding ontologies to align with evolving government terminology and policies. In this

direction, the proposed ontology is based on a modular (easily extendable) structure, enabling it to accommodate to the evolving nature of public administration (e.g., addition of new document types). This modular design allows for the incremental addition of new transaction/events and their corresponding entities without affecting the main structure.

As future work we plan to include more concepts related to travel approvals (e.g., reason, expense and transport mode of a trip) as well as relations to other acts in DIAVGEIA (e.g., a "Travel approval" act is related to a "Credit commitment" act). We also plan to link the returned results to existing vocabularies and ontologies (e.g., the origin/destination locations can be linked to equivalent dbpedia concepts and the transport mode can be linked to the Transport mode³ controlled vocabulary) providing more meaningfully context. We also plan to apply and evaluate the proposed approach using more act types (e.g., budget approvals, project assignments).

A limitation of the proposed approach is the fact that it requires manual evaluation, thus it cannot easily scale. As future work we plan to exploit existing metadata published at DIAVGEIA using them as ground truth for evaluation. For some act types (e.g., project assignment) DIAVGEIA provides metadata for the transaction/event

³<https://mobilitydcat-ap.github.io/controlled-vocabularies/transport-mode/1.0.0/>

(e.g., name of the assignee, amount). Such metadata can be used to automate the evaluation and evaluate at large scale.

In the frame of the paper we used a zero-shot prompt approach. As future work we plan to use and evaluate other prompting approaches (few-shot, chain of thought etc) and prompt designs (e.g., provide the structure of the ontology in the prompt as RDF or JSON code). Considering the fact that some LLMs (like Mistral 7B) had trouble with irrelevant outputs and format inconsistencies, any prompting approach that can address this variability could improve the robustness of the approach and potentially allow more consistent performance across different LLMs.

Overall, the proposed approach contributes to the fields of information extraction and e-government, particularly for its focus on language-specific, zero-shot learning applications. It sets a solid foundation for transforming government document repositories into structured, queryable datasets, ultimately aiding transparency and efficiency in public administration. In this direction, we anticipate that the proposed approach will enable the transformation of DIAVGEIA from a document-centric to a data-centric portal.

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